

The Dam Xayaburi and the Need to Review the 1995 Mekong River Basin Agreement

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Abstract:

This paper will review the development of Mekong hydropower, analyze the shortcomings of the Mekong Agreement and discuss the importance of change to the 1995 Agreement as appropriate solutions to this problem.

Keywords: Mekong hydropower, the dam Xayaburi.

1. INTRODUCTION

The lower Mekong, one of the last big untamed rivers in the world,¹ has been facing the challenge of being dammed driven by the national interest of its riparian countries. In September 2010, Laos notified the Mekong River Commission of a proposed mainstream Mekong hydropower development project in Xayaburi Province.² The proposed Xayaburi dam has led to concerns about the huge environmental and social risks of the project. If the Xayaburi dam is built, it will set a precedent for building a cascade of 10 other dams on the mainstream of the Lower Mekong.³ It will also significantly affect the food security of Cambodia and Vietnam downstream⁴ and cause negative impacts on the river ecology and biodiversity.⁵ Although the stipulated Mekong River Commission Procedures for Notification, Prior Consultation and Agreement require 'available and additional technical data and information on its proposed use of waters for an evaluation of impacts',⁶ Laos has not yet provided sufficient data on the impacts of the proposed Xayaburi project to make an informed decision possible.⁷ Additionally, because the Xayaburi project is likely to cause significant transboundary environmental harm to downstream countries, Laos is also required to conduct a Transboundary Environmental Impact Assessment but this has not been conducted.⁸ Although the Xayaburi project was delayed for at least ten years of further study on social and environmental impacts by a decision of the Mekong River Commission Council on 8 December 2011, it was probably temporary. In 2012 the Laos government decided to proceed with the project, but Cambodia and Vietnam are not legally empowered to stop it under the 1995 Agreement on the Cooperation for Sustainable Development of the Mekong River Basin (hereafter referred as the Mekong Agreement).⁹ This shortcoming of the Mekong Agreement leads to the need to reform the Mekong Agreement's legal and institutional framework.

¹ Gayathri Vaidyanathan, 'Remaking the Mekong: scientists are hoping to stall plans to erect a string of dams along the Mekong River' (2011) 478(7369) (2011/10/20) *Nature* 305, 305.

² Mekong River Commission (MRC), *MRC receives first notification of mainstream Mekong project*, 22 September 2010, MRC Mekong River Commission, <<http://www.mrcmekong.org/news-and-events/news/mrc-receives-first-notification-of-mainstream-mekong-project-2/>>.

³ Vaidyanathan, above n 1, 305.

⁴ See, eg, Earthrights International, *Xayaburi poses test for Mekong regional cooperation*, 7 October 2011, Earthrights International <<http://www.earthrights.org/blog/xayaburi-dam-poses-test-mekong-regional-cooperation>>.

⁵ See, eg, R. Edward Grumbine and Jianchu Xu, 'Mekong Hydropower Development' (2011) 332(6026) (April 8, 2011) *Science* 178, 178.

⁶ Mekong River Commission, *Procedures for Notification, Prior Consultation and Agreement*, 30 November 2003, 5 [5.2.1].

⁷ See, eg, Earthrights International n 4; see, eg, International Rivers, *Sidestepping science: Review of the Porry Report on the Xayaburi Dam*, November 2011, Earthright International, <<http://www.internationalrivers.org/files/Intl%20Rivers%20analysis%20of%20Pory%20Xayaburi%20report%20Nov%202011.pdf>>; see, eg, Vaidyanathan, above n 1, 305.

⁸ Mekong River Commission, *Lower Mekong countries take prior consultation on Xayaburi project to ministerial level*, 19 April 2011, MRC Mekong River Commission, <<http://www.mrcmekong.org/news-and-events/news/lower-mekong-countries-take-prior-consultation-on-xayaburi-project-to-ministerial-level/>>; see also, International Rivers, *Laos steamrolls neighbors in Xayaburi dams process*, 23 June 2011, International Rivers, <<http://www.internationalrivers.org/2011-6-22/laos-steamrolls-neighbors-xayaburi-dam-process>>; see, eg, Earthrights International above n 4.

⁹ Earthrights International, *A Reprieve on the Mekong: Xayaburi Dam Project Delayed... For Now*, 22 April 2011, Earthrights International, <<http://www.earthrights.org/blog/reprieve-mekong-xayaburi-dam-project-delayed>>.

Introducing additional protocols also needs to be taken into consideration when reviewing the agreement. This paper will review the development of Mekong hydropower, analyze the shortcomings of the Mekong Agreement and discuss the importance of change to the 1995 Agreement as appropriate solutions to this problem.

2. AN OVERVIEW OF THE MEKONG RIVER BASIN

The Mekong River originates in Tibet and flows through the territories of six countries: China, Myanmar, Laos, Thailand, Cambodia, and Vietnam. The Mekong with a basin area of approximately 800,000 square kilometers, a total length of about 4,620 km,¹⁰ is one of the most important rivers in the world. The source of the Mekong is from the snowcapped Tibetan mountains. In addition to this, rainfall, temperature cycle and two monsoons contribute to its annual flooding as the most outstanding feature of the river.¹¹ The river carries out approximately 450 billion cubic meters of water annually.¹² Equivalent to 18 percent of the total volume of water flows through the upper basin within the territories of China and Myanmar. The remaining 82 percent of the total volume of water is the annual discharge of the lower basin within four riparian countries: Laos, Thailand, Cambodia, and Vietnam.¹³

Figure 1. The main rivers and national boundaries of the Mekong region

Source: United Nations map number 4112 Rev.2 January 2004

¹⁰ See Hiroshi Hori, *The Mekong: Environment and Development* (United Nations University Press, 2000) 1.

¹¹ Ibid 24-36; see also Van Duyen Nguyen, 'The Inadequacy of Environmental Protection Mechanisms in the Mekong River Basin Agreement' (2001) 6(3/4) *Asia Pacific Journal of Environmental Law* 349, 350.

¹² Hori, above n 10, 29.

¹³ Ibid 29.

More than 70 million people live in the Mekong River Basin and more than 60 million of them live in lower basin countries of Cambodia, Laos, Thailand, and Vietnam.¹⁴ 85 percent of the Mekong Basin inhabitants make their living directly from the natural resources of the Mekong River by fishing and irrigated rice production.¹⁵ Many lakes and wetlands along the river are major sources of fish for the riparian people.¹⁶ Fishery resources form an important part in the livelihoods of the Lower Mekong Basin inhabitants, especially for people living in Cambodia and the delta region of Vietnam.¹⁷ Considered as the largest freshwater fishery in the world, the Mekong River provides 2.5 million tonnes of fish per year, valued at between US\$ 3 billion to \$6 billion.¹⁸ It is believed that 50 percent to 75 percent of the lower Mekong Basin residents' total intake of protein is from fish of the river.¹⁹

The Mekong Delta spreads out the border region between Vietnam and Cambodia with an area of roughly 5.9 million hectares.²⁰ Most of the Mekong Delta, 4 million hectares in a total of 5.9 million hectares, is within Vietnamese territory.²¹ Accounting for 20 percent of the total Vietnamese land and supporting for more than 18 million local people,²² the Mekong Delta is one of the most productive zones for rice and aquaculture in the world. The delta supplies more than 70 and 50 percent staple of rice and aquaculture respectively for Vietnam's foreign export of these products.²³

The Mekong and its tributaries play an important role not only in the livelihoods of the riparian inhabitants but also for the ecology and biodiversity of the Mekong region. The Mekong's seasonal variation in water levels creates a rich and extensive series of wetlands in the Lower Mekong Basin.²⁴ The river and its tributaries, along with lakes support many unique ecosystems and a wide range of globally-threatened species. With between 500 and 1,300 species of fish inhabiting the river and its associated wetlands, the biodiversity of the Mekong River fauna is the third largest world ecosystem.²⁵

One of the potential benefits of the Mekong River is its capacity to produce hydroelectric power. The total hydroelectric potential of the Mekong Basin is 1,170,000 MW, divided between 665,000 MW in the upper basin and 505,000 MW in the lower basin.²⁶ In the lower basin, it is estimated that with 12 planned mainstream dams, 14,697 MW power could be generated.²⁷ These amounts of power are believed to provide enough to satisfy the demand for electricity in a country like Thailand for the next 15 to 20 years.²⁸ In recent years, the demand for electricity has grown significantly in the Mekong region due to rapid industrialization, export-led economic growth, and expanded domestic consumption.²⁹ This trend obviously leads riparian countries to plan for potential hydroelectric power exploitation of the Mekong River without significantly regarding the huge risks for the environment and rural communities.³⁰ Of course, damming the Mekong River brings riparian countries not only hydroelectric power but also benefits irrigation and flood

¹⁴ See, eg, *ibid* 11-2; see, eg, Jeffrey W. Jacobs, 'The Mekong River Commission: Transboundary water resources planning and regional security' (2002) 168(00167398) *The Geographical Journal* 354, 356.

¹⁵ Jacobs, above n n 14, 356.

¹⁶ See Hori, above n 10, 54-60; see also Kite Geoff, 'Modelling the Mekong: hydrological simulation for environmental impact studies' (2001) 253(1-4) *Journal of Hydrology* 1, 1.

¹⁷ Hori, above n 10, 54-60.

¹⁸ Loei Chiang Khan, 'Water wars: The drive to develop and consume pose threats to the Great Mekong River', *AsiaNews* (Bangkok), January 27 - February 9 2012, 8, 8.

¹⁹ Hori, above n 10, 56; but see Geoff, above n 16, 1

²⁰ Francois Molle, Tira Foran and Mira Käkönen (eds), *Contested waterscapes in the Mekong Region: hydropower, livelihoods and governance* (Earthscan, 2009) 206.

²¹ *Ibid*.

²² *Ibid*; see also Nguyen, above n 11, 351.

²³ Francois Molle, Tira Foran and Mira Käkönen (eds), above n 20, 207.

²⁴ Alebel Abebe Belay et al, 'The Challenges of Integrated Management of Mekong River Basin in Terms of People's Livelihood' (2010) 02(01) *Journal of Water Resource and Protection* 61, 61.

²⁵ *Ibid*.

²⁶ Hori, above n 10, 71.

²⁷ Khan, above n 18, 9.

²⁸ *Ibid*.

²⁹ Francois Molle, Tira Foran and Mira Käkönen (eds), above n 20 24.

³⁰ *Ibid* 23-6.

control which are very important for farming and living security of its inhabitants.³¹ However, it is also very important for the lower Mekong River countries to pay more attention to the environmental and social impacts as well as the economic benefit of damming the river.

3. HISTORY OF COOPERATION AND DAM DEVELOPMENT IN THE MEKONG RIVER BASIN

In the early 1950s, the United Nation Economic Commission for Asia and the Far East (ECAFE) began to survey the lower Mekong Basin mainly aiming at the control of flooding in the Mekong Delta; however, its primary rationale was subsequently changed to provide for additional objectives including irrigation, hydroelectric power generation, navigation and the development of fisheries.³² Along with the United Nations' first survey, by 1955, the United States Bureau of Reclamation (USBR) conducted a study that concluded that the river should be dammed for navigation, irrigation, and hydropower.³³ As most of the upper Mekong River belongs to territory of China, the country then taken over by communism, and while the US wanted to treat Southeast Asia as a frontier to hinder the spread of communism, this study focused only on the four lower Mekong River countries (Thailand, Laos, Cambodia, and Vietnam).³⁴ The geopolitical situation of the region in the 1950s was an obstacle to the study of the entire Mekong River in terms of development and cooperation.³⁵ However, both ECAFE and USBR realized the importance of cooperation among the four lower basin countries regarding water resources management.³⁶

In October 1957, the Mekong Committee was established with its primary objectives of 'formulation, investigation, coordination, supervision, and control of water resources development plans for the Lower Mekong Basin.'³⁷

At the beginning of dam development in the Mekong River, the USBR's study recommended five priority projects for the Mekong.³⁸ In addition to this, during the period between 1959 and 1960, research supported by the Japanese government proposed numerous dam projects for the major tributaries of the Mekong.³⁹ All these projects thereafter became part of the first major basin-wide development plan of the Mekong Committee published in 1970 – the Indicative Basin Plan (IBP). The plan outlined 180 possible projects on the mainstream and the tributaries with four-category purposes: irrigation, hydroelectric power generation, flood control, and navigation.⁴⁰ In the plan, 17 mainstream projects were proposed but reconnaissance work was done only at five project sites due to the budget was restraint. At that time, international cooperation increased concerning the study of dams in the Mekong lower basin. Feasibility studies for some dam projects were conducted with help from the governments of the US, Australia, Thailand, Laos, Canada, Japan, and the Philippines.⁴¹ However, these outlined mainstream dam projects

³¹ For example, hundred thousands of hectares of farmland were irrigated by dams on major tributaries improving the productivities of agriculture, contributing to higher living standard of millions of riparian residents. See Hori, above n 10, 166-87.

³² See, eg, *ibid* 82-3; see, eg, Francois Molle, Tira Foran and Mira Käkönen (eds), above n 20, 4.

³³ See, eg, Tira Foran and Mira Käkönen (eds), above n 20, 4-5; see, eg, Nguyen, above n 11, 352.

³⁴ See, eg, Tira Foran and Mira Käkönen (eds), above n 20, 4; see, eg, Hori, above n 10, 82; 'China has never been a member of either the Mekong Committee nor of its successor the MRC. Nonmembership of the Mekong Committee was established in 1950s and rose to prominence in the 1960s under U.S. hegemony during the cold war, at a time when China was firmly in the opposite camp.'; see, eg, Philip Hirsch, 'Water Governance Reform and Catchment Management in the Mekong Region' (2006) 15(2) (June 1, 2006) *The Journal of Environment & Development* 184, 189; see, eg, Jacobs, above n 14, 356.

³⁵ See, eg, Hori, above n 10, 103. 'At the time, China was not a member of the United Nations, while Burma (now Myanmar) did not show any interest in discussions on cooperative development.'; see, eg, Hirsch, above n 34, 189.

³⁶ See, eg, Hori, above n 10, 83; see, eg, Tira Foran and Mira Käkönen (eds), above n 20, 4-5.

³⁷ Hori, above n 10, 83.

³⁸ See especially Hori, above n 10, 82-4. These five priority projects for the Mekong consist of four mainstream dam projects namely the Pa Mong Dam project, the Khemarat project (both in Laos), the Khone Falls project (at the Laos-Cambodia border), and the Sambor project (in Cambodia). The remaining project is a large-scale project on the Tonle Sap river; Cf Tira Foran and Mira Käkönen (eds), above n 20, 4-5. The USBR's study recommended three top-priority projects: the Pa Mong Dam, the Sambor Dam and the Tonle Sap Dam.

³⁹ Hori, above n 10, 84.

⁴⁰ See Tira Foran and Mira Käkönen (eds), above n 20, 26. Cf Hori, above n 10, 136. 'The plan outlined a total of 17 mainstream projects and 87 tributary projects.'

⁴¹ *Ibid*.

which were impossible to carry out because of the Vietnam War and the Cambodian conflict during the 1970s.⁴²

After the Vietnam War, Cambodia withdrew from the Mekong Committee; the US and the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) stopped funding the dam development in the Lower Mekong River.⁴³ This caused significant change to the working base of the Mekong Committee and the plans for dam development. In 1978, the three remaining country members formed the Interim Committee for Coordination of Investigations of the Lower Mekong Basin (the Interim Committee).⁴⁴ After that, the Interim Committee continued to study the development of dams when proposing a cascade of eight dams on the mainstream in a revised Indicative Basin Plan published in 1987. These eight dams were considered 'as the best option for the long-term development of the basin's water resources'.⁴⁵ However, a lack of financial support from Western countries along with the political situation in Indochina was an obstacle for cooperation on water resources development in the lower basin at this time. The Perspectives for Mekong Development, another revised plan, which was approved in 1988 continued to aim at proposing a cascade of eight dams on the mainstream of the Lower Mekong.⁴⁶ In 1990, the Interim Committee carried out another study regarding the potential for mainstream development: Mekong Mainstream Development Possibilities: Summary Report. Although the report did not offer any changes in the overall configuration of the Mekong development project, it concluded that there was a need for more studies on social and environmental impacts of implementing the Mekong development project.⁴⁷

The year 1995 saw a significant change in the cooperation concerning the lower Mekong basin. On 5 April 1995, the Mekong Agreement was signed by all four lower riparian countries: Thailand, Laos, Vietnam, and Cambodia. Under the Agreement, the principles of regional cooperation were codified and the Mekong River Commission was established.⁴⁸ Dam development has continuously become one of the top agenda items of the Mekong River Commission since its establishment. Article 24 of the Mekong Agreement mandates the Mekong River Commission to formulate a basin development plan.⁴⁹ According to the Basin Development Strategy, published in March 2011, over the next 20 years, 12 mainstream dams and 30 tributary dams are planned.⁵⁰

4. THE MEKONG AGREEMENT AND ITS MECHANISM REGARDING DAM CONSTRUCTION

Although many dams have been built on tributaries of the Lower Mekong River and there are a number of studies about environmental and social impacts of dams on the tributaries, these did not get much attention from regional operation because most of the tributary dams are within individual nationals. However, Ziv et al (2012) have concluded in one of the newest studies about hydropower in the Mekong River Basin that if all 78 tributary dams (not including mainstream dams) were built, this would generate less energy and cause 'greater environmental risk than the construction of just the upper six mainstream dams on the lower Mekong River'.⁵¹ This conclusion has a special significance in terms of implementing the mechanism of the Mekong Agreement. That is because the Mekong Agreement requires prior consultation and agreement by the Joint Committee for only projects on the mainstream whereas tributary

⁴² Ibid 136.

⁴³ See, eg, Tira Foran and Mira Käkönen (eds), above n 20, 8; see, eg, Hori, above n 10, 166.

⁴⁴ See, eg Tira Foran and Mira Käkönen (eds), above n 20, 8.

⁴⁵ Ibid 9.

⁴⁶ Hori, above n 10, 174-6.

⁴⁷ Tira Foran and Mira Käkönen (eds), above n 20, 9.

⁴⁸ See, eg, Philip Hirsch et al, 'National Interests and Transboundary Water Governance in the Mekong' (Australian Mekong Resource Centre, 2006) <http://sydney.edu.au/mekong/documents/mekwatgov_mainreport.pdf> 19; see, eg, Tira Foran and Mira Käkönen (eds), above n 20, 10.

⁴⁹ *Agreement on the Cooperation for the Sustainable Development of the Mekong River Basin*, opened for signature 5 April 1995, 2069 UNTS 3 (entered into force 5 April 1995) ('*Mekong Agreement*') art 24.

⁵⁰ Mekong River Commission, 'Basin Development Strategy 2011-2015' (Mekong River Commission, 2011) <<http://www.mrcmekong.org/assets/Publications/strategies-workprog/Strategic-Plan-2011-2015-council-approved25012011-final.pdf>> 14.

⁵¹ Guy Ziv et al, 'Trading-off fish biodiversity, food security, and hydropower in the Mekong River Basin' (2012) 1 <<http://www.pnas.org/content/early/2012/03/05/1201423109>> 1.

projects just need a notification to the Joint Committee before proceeding.⁵² The next section will analyze the Mekong Agreement and its mechanism regarding environmental protection and social security in general. It is also necessary to focus on the mechanism of procedures for building a dam on the river.

4.1. The Mekong Agreement and the Procedures for Notification, Prior Consultation, and Agreement

4.1.1. The Geopolitical Context of the Mekong Agreement

The Mekong Agreement was signed on 5 April 1995 after several years negotiating and bargaining among the four riparian countries, especially between Vietnam and Thailand regarding Thailand's plan to divert the main river channel for irrigation purposes.⁵³ The Mekong Agreement represents the national interests of riparian countries in the regional geopolitical arena. As an upstream country, Thailand is primarily interested in irrigation for the arid northeastern portion of the country. In addition, Thailand is in favour of Lao's development plan of hydropower on the river because it will take advantage of importing power from Laos in order to supply its huge demand for energy.⁵⁴ Considered as the aspiring battery of Southeast Asia, Laos is extremely interested in exploiting hydropower of the Mekong.⁵⁵ With an estimated 18,000 MW of hydropower potential, exporting electricity to high-demand energy neighbors such as Thailand, China and Vietnam is expected to make a great contribution to Laos' economy.⁵⁶

Consequently, when forming the Mekong Agreement, Thailand and Laos are not in favour of introducing strict rules relating to the construction of dams on the Mekong and its tributaries.⁵⁷ In contrast, Vietnam is concerned about the role of upstream dams on the increasing salinization of the Mekong Delta, where roughly 50 percent of its rice crop is produced while Cambodia expresses its growing concern about the well-being of Tonle Sap Lake caused by the negative impacts of upstream dams.⁵⁸ From this context, the Mekong Agreement is considered a product of regional politics rather than the global cold war interests that influenced the earlier Mekong Committee.⁵⁹

⁵² *Mekong Agreement*, above n 50, art 5; see also *ibid*.

⁵³ Chris Sneddon and Coleen Fox, 'Power, Development, and Institutional Change: Participatory Governance in the Lower Mekong Basin' (2007) 35(12) *World Development* 2161, 2167.

⁵⁴ *Ibid*; see also Foran and Mira Käkönen (eds), above n 20, 29-31.

⁵⁵ Foran and Mira Käkönen (eds), above n 20, 31.

⁵⁶ *Ibid* 31-4.

⁵⁷ Oliver Hensengerth, 'Transboundary River Cooperation and the Regional Public Good: The Case of the Mekong River' (2009) 31(2) *Contemporary Southeast Asia* 326, 328-9.

⁵⁸ *Ibid* 329.

⁵⁹ Philip Hirsch, 'Beyond the nation state: natural resource conflict and "national interest" in Mekong hydropower development' (1999) 29(3) *Golden Gate University Law Review* 399, 406.

4.1.2. Institutional Framework

Figure 2. Mekong River Commission organizational structure

Under the Mekong Agreement, the Mekong River Commission (MRC) was established with the role to promote cooperation in all fields of sustainable development, utilization, conservation and management of the water and related resources of the Basin.⁶⁰ The MRC has three permanent bodies: the Council, the Joint Committee, and the Secretariat.⁶¹ The Council consists of one member from each participating riparian State, who is at Ministerial or Cabinet-level and empowered to make policy decisions on behalf of his or her government.⁶² The functions of the Council are to decide on policy matters necessary to implement the Agreement, to make policy to promote and support cooperative activities and to solve disputes referred to it.⁶³ The Joint Committee consists of one member from each participating riparian State at no less than Head of Department level. Its functions include *inter alia* the formulation of the basin development plan, the update, and exchange of information, the conduct of appropriate studies and assessment for the protection of the environment and the maintenance of the ecological balance of the Mekong River Basin.⁶⁴ The Secretariat renders technical and administrative services to the Council and Joint Committee and is under the supervision of the Joint Committee.⁶⁵

4.1.3. The Procedures for Notification, Prior Consultation, and Agreement

Article 5 of the Mekong Agreement stipulates the requirement for any proposed water use projects of the Mekong River on both its mainstream and tributaries to which the process of notification, prior consultation and/or agreement is needed among riparian States at the Joint Committee level.⁶⁶ More than eight years after the establishment of the Mekong Agreement, on 31 November 2003, MRC Council approved the Procedures for Notification, Prior Consultation, and Agreement (PNPCA). This was one of the efforts of MRC in order to continue to cooperate and promote in a constructive and mutually beneficial manner in the utilization and development of the Mekong River Basin water and related resources as

⁶⁰ *Mekong Agreement*, above n 50.

⁶¹ *Mekong Agreement*, above n 50, art 11.

⁶² *Ibid* art 15.

⁶³ *Ibid* art 18.

⁶⁴ *Ibid* art 24.

⁶⁵ *Ibid* art 28.

⁶⁶ *Ibid* art 5; see also Mekong River Commission, *Procedures for Notification, Prior Consultation and Agreement (PNPCA) Proposed Xayaburi Dam Project – Mekong River: Prior Consultation Project Review Report*, 24 March 2011, MRC Mekong River Commission, <<http://www.mrcmekong.org/assets/Publications/Reports/PC-Proj-Review-Report-Xaiyaburi-24-3-11.pdf>>.

recognized in the Mekong Agreement. The notification requirement and procedures are required for proposed uses of intra-basin use and inter-basin diversion on the tributaries, including the Tonle Sap, and intra-basin use during the wet season on the mainstream.⁶⁷ The Notification includes feasibility study report, implementation plan, schedule, and all available data and it is prepared by the National Mekong Committee before transmitting to the MRC Joint Committee through the MRC Secretariat.⁶⁸ Unlike the Notification, the Prior Consultation aims at arriving at an agreement and is required for three following proposed uses:

- * Inter-basin diversion from mainstream during the wet season;
- * Intra-basin use on the mainstream during the dry season; and
- * Inter-basin diversion of the surplus quantity of water during the dry season.⁶⁹

In addition to the data and information required for Notification, the notifying State is also required to provide the MRC Joint Committee with available and additional technical data and information on its proposed use of waters for an evaluation of impacts by the other riparian States.⁷⁰ The process for Prior Consultation consists of three stages. First, the National Mekong Committee of the notifying State(s) submits documents for Prior Consultation on any proposed use of water to the MRC Joint Committee through the MRC Secretariat. Once the documents are received, the MRC Secretariat *shall* transmit copies of the documents to the other Member State(s) for their evaluation and reply.⁷¹ Second, the other member(s) evaluate the proposed use and reply to the MRC Joint Committee through MRC Secretariat following receipt of the documents from the notifying State(s). At this stage, if necessary the notified State(s) may request additional information, a consultation or presentation, and/or a field visit to the project site in order to evaluate the possible impacts of the proposed use. During this stage, if requested, notifying States(s) are responsible for providing available data and information.⁷² Third, after discussing and evaluating the proposed use, the MRC Joint Committee will issue a decision that contains agreed conditions. The notifying State(s) shall not implement the proposed use without providing the opportunity to the other member States to discuss and evaluate the proposed use.⁷³

4.2. The Weaknesses of the Mekong Agreement Regarding Dam Building

In the light of recent developments in international water law, five weaknesses of the Mekong Agreement are recognized.⁷⁴ Firstly, although the Mekong Agreement has an article in which any other riparian state, accepting the rights and obligations under the Agreement, may become a party with the consent of the parties,⁷⁵ China and Myanmar, both Mekong riparian states, have not become parties yet. The absence of China and Myanmar is the most important shortcoming of the Agreement.⁷⁶ Chinese territory accounts for approximately 21 percent of the entire Basin,⁷⁷ and the upper basin (China and Myanmar) covers approximately 24 percent of the total basin area.⁷⁸ Obviously, China and Myanmar play an important role in the development of the basin, but neither member states of the Mekong Agreement. The second limitation of the Mekong Agreement is that the Agreement is not efficient in terms of supporting the legitimate interests of downstream states such as Cambodia and Vietnam.⁷⁹ The Agreement does not clearly define the

⁶⁷ *Mekong Agreement*, above n 50, art 5; MRC, *Procedures for Notification, Prior Consultation and Agreement*, (2003) section 4.

⁶⁸ *Ibid.*

⁶⁹ *Ibid* section 5.1.

⁷⁰ *Ibid* section 5.2.

⁷¹ *Ibid* section 5.4.1.

⁷² *Ibid* section 5.4.2.

⁷³ *Ibid* section 5.4.3.

⁷⁴ Nguyen, above n 11, 364-6.

⁷⁵ *Mekong Agreement*, above n 50, art 39.

⁷⁶ Hensengerth, above n 58, 330. See also Hirsch, above n 60, 407.

⁷⁷ Hori, above n 10, 11.

⁷⁸ *Ibid.*

⁷⁹ Nguyen, above n 11, 365.

responsibility between the upstream and downstream states.⁸⁰ Thirdly, by not providing an effective procedure to address the impacts of development on the environment, the Mekong Agreement does not specifically define the principles of sustainable use of water in contrast with the Watercourses Convention.⁸¹ Fourthly, there is no binding general obligation in the Mekong Agreement that requires watercourses states to cooperate on the basis of mutual benefit and good faith while the Watercourses Convention imposes an obligation for this.⁸² Finally, by stipulating prior consultation as neither a right to veto the use nor a unilateral right to use water by any riparian without taking into account other riparians' rights, the Mekong Agreement fails to protect the interest of the two downstream Mekong states, Cambodia and Vietnam.⁸³ In other words, the Mekong Agreement is designed in a way that encourages Thailand and Laos to build dams for hydropower and irrigation purposes regardless of the interest of Cambodia and Vietnam.⁸⁴ In terms of dam building, the two main points which clearly emphasize the weaknesses of the 1995 Agreement, as discussed below are the absence of China as an upstream riparian member state and the lack of mechanisms to protect the equal rights of the downstream countries.

4.2.1. The Absence of China as an upper riparian

In recent decades, China has become one of the fastest-growing economies in the world. Its economic growth has caused great demand for energy; therefore China needs to develop its own energy supply as much as possible as importing energy is no longer economically feasible.⁸⁵ In this context, building dams on the Mekong River is the best choice for China to generate electricity in order to feed its energy need for economic growth. It is estimated that building dams on the Mekong River can supply about seventy percent of China's current electricity needs.⁸⁶ As an upstream riparian, China can take full advantage of utilizing the Mekong River while does not want to take responsibility for any harm that it might do to the other downstream riparians. China obviously does not want to be bound by an agreement in which it is not free to dam the River as it wants. On the other hand, during the formation of the Mekong Agreement, an informal meeting among all six Mekong Basin states was proposed by the Thai government as Thailand saw the direct impacts of future Chinese projects on the Mekong River in Thai territory. However, the Vietnamese are not in favour of creating a Mekong regime with all six Basin states since Vietnam is concerned that Chinese membership would probably shift the balance of power toward the upper Basin states.⁸⁷ Although a meeting among officials from the five other states was held in Chiang Mai, Thailand on March 1992, there was no improvement made since Laos and Cambodia were not interested in proceeding without Vietnam.⁸⁸

No one can confirm what would be the outcome of any negotiations between the six Mekong countries. Yet, the downstream riparians have regrets because they have lost the opportunity to obtain the participation of China in the process of negotiations in forming the 1995 Agreement. Although the 1995 Agreement remains open for the participation of China and Myanmar, it is not easy to predict whether China would ever participate in the Mekong regime as a full member since it has built a series of large dams on the upper Mekong River. Additionally, in the negotiation of forming the 1995 Agreement, China and Myanmar did not see any benefits in joining the Mekong regime.⁸⁹ The absence of China from the 1995 Agreement is

⁸⁰ Ibid. In comparison with The Convention on the Law of Non-Navigational Uses of International Watercourses ('Watercourses Convention'), the Mekong Agreement does not define the roles and responsibilities of the Joint Committee. In terms of water use projects, the Mekong Agreement creates different treatment between intra-basin projects and inter-basin projects. This treatment does not appear in the Watercourses Convention.

⁸¹ Ibid 366.

⁸² Ibid; see also *Convention on the Law of the Non-Navigational Uses of International Watercourse*, opened for signature 21 May 1997, 36 ILM 700 (not yet in force) ('Watercourses Convention') art 8.

⁸³ Nguyen, above n 11, 366 ; see also *Mekong Agreement*, above n 50, chap II.

⁸⁴ Nguyen, above n 11, 366.

⁸⁵ Joshua D. Freeman, 'Taming the Mekong: The possibilities and Pitfalls of a Mekong Basin Joint Energy Development Agreement' (2009) 10(2) *Asian-Pacific Law & Policy Journal* 453, 453

⁸⁶ Ibid.

⁸⁷ G. Browder, 'An Analysis of the Negotiations for the 1995 Mekong Agreement' (2000) 5(2) *International Negotiation* 237, 247.

⁸⁸ Ibid.

⁸⁹ Tun Myint, 'Democracy in global environmental governance: issues, interests, and actors in the Mekong and the Rhine' (2003) 10(1) (2003 Winter) *Indiana Journal of Global Legal Studies* 287, 299

inevitable leave as is typical of the upstream countries where it can take full advantages of utilizing the Rivers regardless of the interests of other downstream countries.

4.2.2. *The lack of mechanisms for the equal rights of the downstream countries*

Unlikely the Mekong Committee regime (1957), when all member states had the veto power on water utilization of the River by any member,⁹⁰ the 1995 Agreement has become a step backwards compared to previous mechanisms, as Article 5 of the Mekong Agreement only stipulates the requirement of any proposed water use projects of the Mekong River on both its mainstream and tributaries to which the process of notification, prior consultation and/or agreement is needed among riparian States at the Joint Committee level.⁹¹ In the process of negotiation for forming the 1995 Agreement, as an upstream member Thailand did not want to reactivate the rules of the Mekong Committee statute. The Thai government felt that the mandate of the Mekong Committee to control the water project would not reflect Thai interests.⁹² In fact, Thailand really did not want to give the other Mekong states the right to veto Thai water resource development projects.⁹³ During this progress, Thailand was pursuing a policy similar to China as a typical upstream country. The absence of a veto right of member states to others' water use in the 1995 Agreement made it be less constraining for Thailand than the statute of 1957. In addition to this, as mentioned above, in the negotiations for forming the 1995 Mekong Agreement, it was believed that Laos, Cambodia, and Vietnam were allies.⁹⁴ However, the original alliance was temporary until a difference among their national interests arose when Laos, an upstream country, (in comparison with Cambodia and Vietnam), launched the first mainstream Mekong hydropower dam (Xayabury dam) in 2010 by notifying the Mekong River Commission under the stipulation of Article 5 of the 1995 Agreement and the Mekong River Commission Procedures for Notification, Prior Consultation, and Agreement. Although at the Mekong River Commission Council meeting on 8th December 2011, the members agreed that there is a need for further study on the sustainable development and management of the Mekong River including the impact from mainstream hydropower development projects, there have been signs that Laos has continued the construction of the project regardless of the Council's agreement.⁹⁵ Despite unresolved concerns with the Xayaburi dam, Laos has begun work on its second hydropower dam on the mainstream of the Mekong River, the Don Sahong dam, even though the project has not yet undergone the PNPCA.⁹⁶ These activities of the Lao government are indications that the 1995 Agreement completely lacks legal obligation to the parties. As a result, the interests of downstream countries are seriously affected in both the environment and social terms.

There is no particular article stipulating the construction of a dam in the 1995 Agreement. However, this is generally mentioned in the Article 1 (Areas of Cooperation). The cooperation is in all fields of sustainable development, utilization, management and conservation of the water and related resources of the Mekong River Basin including, but not limited to irrigation, hydro-power, navigation, flood control, fisheries, timber floating, recreation and tourism, in a manner to optimize the multiple-use and mutual benefits of all riparians and to minimize the harmful effects that might result from natural occurrences and man-made activities.⁹⁷ It can be explained that dam building is one of the activities the member states need to be taken into account when utilizing the water resources of the Mekong River. The 1995 Agreement also

⁹⁰ John Dore and Louis Lebel, 'Deliberation and Scale in Mekong Region Water Governance' (2010) 46(1) *Environmental Management* 60, 67.

⁹¹ *Mekong Agreement*, above n 50, art 5; see also Mekong River Commission, *Procedures for Notification, Prior Consultation and Agreement (PNPCA) Proposed Xayaburi Dam Project – Mekong River: Prior Consultation Project Review Report*, 24 March 2011, MRC Mekong River Commission, < <http://www.mrcmekong.org/assets/Publications/Reports/PC-Proj-Review-Report-Xaiyaburi-24-3-11.pdf>>.

⁹² Browder, above n 88, 244.

⁹³ *Ibid* 245.

⁹⁴ *Ibid* 247.

⁹⁵ International Rivers, *As consultant distances itself, cracks appear in Laos' portrayal of Xayabury Dam*, 8th September 2012, International Rivers, < <http://www.internationalrivers.org/blogs/267/as-consultant-distances-itself-cracks-appear-in-laos%E2%80%99-portrayal-of-xayaburi-dam>>.

⁹⁶ International Rivers, *Laos begins work on the second Mekong River Dam*, 2th September 2012, International Rivers, < <http://www.internationalrivers.org/resources/laos-begins-work-on-a-second-mekong-river-dam-7663>>.

⁹⁷ *Mekong Agreement*, above n 50, art 1.

stipulates that member states are responsible for making every effort to avoid, minimize and mitigate harmful effects that might occur to the environment, especially the water quantity and quality, the aquatic (eco-system) conditions, and the ecological balance of the river system, from the development and use of the Mekong River Basin water resources or the discharge of wastes and return flows. Where one or more states are notified with proper and valid evidence that it is causing substantial damage to one or more riparians from the use of and/or discharge to water of the Mekong River, that state or states *shall* cease immediately the alleged cause of harm until such cause of harm is determined in accordance with article 8.⁹⁸

The question remains why Laos has begun the construction of not the Xayabury Dam, but its second hydropower dam and why the Thai government does not strongly oppose the Lao activities. There are two reasons explaining the two governments' attitude towards the construction of dams on the mainstream Mekong River. Firstly, both countries benefit economically if the projects are continued. Laos expects to earn billions of dollars by exporting most of the electricity generated from the projects. Similarly, Thailand, the importer of electricity from the projects, would have access to cheap electricity supply to meet the needs of high energy consumption in the context of the high price of petroleum. Secondly, the 1995 Agreement contains no veto right of members on one others' water use. Although Laos and Thailand violate the principle of sustainable development of the 1995 Agreement, Cambodia and Vietnam, two downstream countries, have no legal instrument to use to prevent the Laos' activities.

In continuing the two dam projects, the Government of Laos appears to be set on unilaterally moving forward with the Xayaburi Dam and the Don Sahong Dam in violation of international law and its commitments under the 1995 Agreement. Laos is also disregarding its regional commitments and robbing the future of millions of people in the region who rely upon the river for their livelihood and food security.⁹⁹

5. CONCLUSION

As discussed above, the 1995 Agreement reveals two main shortcomings in relation to building dams on the Mekong River including the absence of China as an upstream country and the lack of mechanisms for the equal rights of downstream countries. It is very likely that China will never join the Mekong Commission as a full party. The only possibility to deal with the problems of dam building on the Lower Mekong River may be to change to the legal mechanism of the 1995 Agreement or rely on customary international law. As this Agreement was signed in 1995, two years before the signing of the Convention on the Law of the Non-navigational Uses of International Watercourses (the 1997 Convention), some advanced stipulations of the 1997 Convention including the principles of factors relevant to equitable and reasonable utilization, an obligation not to cause significant harm and a general obligation to cooperate did not appear in the 1995 Agreement. Cambodia and Vietnam should persuade the two upstream members Laos and Thailand to revise or add new regulatory provisions implementing advanced stipulations of the 1997 Convention into the existing Agreement. Forming a new legal framework for the PNPCA to fully regard the interests of downstream members is another possible solution although the key point here is that each member has the veto right on others' water utilization.

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⁹⁸ Mekong Agreement, above n 50, art 7.

⁹⁹ International Rivers, *Illegal construction on the Xayabury dam forges ahead*, 4th August 2011, International Rivers, <<http://www.internationalrivers.org/resources/illegal-construction-on-the-xayaburi-dam-forges-ahead-3707>>; see also International Rivers, above n 97.

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